

Livestock and Landscape: an Agro-tourism Value Chain

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Agroforestry landscape in Evrytania – Greece (photo by V. Lappa)

The agri-tourism value chain comprises a set of related activities. These activities take place in the same area and create a very special tourist experience. Traditional extensive grazing and especially the seasonal transhumance of a large number of flocks of goats and sheep, in the mountainous Evrytania, has created the agroforestry landscape of high cultural and ecological values that we enjoy today. Based on extensive grazing and seasonally mobile livestock farming, many opportunities can be created for the development of tourism products.

The agroforestry landscape, undisturbed by intensive human activity, is recognised as one of the strongest indicators of sustainable tourism and its preservation is based on the rational management of natural resources and the continued presence of livestock farmers and herds in the mountains. The special handling by the competent national authorities of the regions that can support such tourist experiences is crucial to improving the services and products they can offer and to their economic development.

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